

An Investigation into the Recent Developments in Intelligent Transport System

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Abstract: Due to increasing reliance on the public transport for clean and sustainable mode of transportation has given new impetus for making public transport more intelligent. The intelligent transport system is the need of the hour as the numbers of the passengers are increasing and accordingly the traffic problem is getting more complex. To resolve this issue many scholars have tried various options like use of big data/artificial intelligence for transport management, use of ICT in transport, Smart Transport system. This review paper is has tried to summarized the findings of the scholars around the world based on the cross sectional study of the relevant papers and systematic literature review of the emerging transport systems based on the published papers from top indexing database of science direct from last 5 years. The findings will help transport policy planner to take wise decisions to solve the problem of transportation.

Keywords: ITC in Transport, Intelligent Transport System, Parallel Transportation and Management System, Vehicular Ad-hoc Networks, Smart Transport System

1. INTRODUCTION

The Intelligent Transport System (ITS) serves as a fundamental aspect of our economy and society, facilitating the smooth functioning of transportation on a daily basis. Over the past few decades, there has been a notable rise in the initiation, development, deployment, and substantial growth of the transport system, resulting in significant impacts on our society and daily lives. Consequently, the concept of the transport system has been redefined as ITS. Traditionally, the research and development of transportation were primarily associated with civil and mechanical engineering. However, in recent times, the scope of ITS has expanded to encompass various disciplines, including computer science engineering. Concepts such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), machine learning, communication, the internet, and emerging engineering and information sciences have become integral to the core of ITS. As a result, ITS can now be defined as a collection of advanced applications that utilize intelligent information and communication technologies to provide services for transport and traffic management. One of the primary objectives of ITS is to address the numerous challenges that have arisen due to population growth, such as air pollution, long travel times, fuel consumption, traffic congestion, and accidents. To tackle these critical issues, ITS organizations are tirelessly working towards finding solutions by focusing on the development of traffic communication and vehicular networking systems (1, 2). By implementing intelligent information and communication technologies, ITS plays a crucial role in mitigating these problems. For instance, through the integration of AI and machine learning, ITS can optimize traffic flow and reduce congestion by providing real-time traffic updates and suggesting alternate routes to drivers. Additionally,

ITS can contribute to reducing air pollution and fuel consumption by promoting the use of electric vehicles and implementing intelligent charging infrastructure. Furthermore, the application of ITS in traffic management systems can enhance safety measures and reduce the occurrence of accidents through the use of intelligent monitoring and surveillance technologies.

1.1 Technologies used in ITS

The area of ITS is supported by three technologies: data collection technologies, communication technologies and common database system. Further advance techniques are also included in ITS which are discussed in literature review. The description of basic technologies is given:

Data collection technologies:

Accurate and comprehensive data collection is a fundamental requirement for the successful implementation of Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS). In recent years, significant advancements have been made in the development and implementation of various techniques aimed at improving data collection methods in the field of transportation.

These data collection technologies can be broadly classified into two main categories: infrastructure-based technology and vehicle-based technology.

Infrastructure-based technology refers to the utilization of physical infrastructure elements to gather data about transportation patterns and behaviors. Some commonly employed infrastructure-based technologies include inductive loops, sensors, and Closed-Circuit Television (CCTV) cameras. Inductive loops are embedded in the road surface and can detect the presence and movement of vehicles by measuring changes in electromagnetic fields. Sensors, on the other hand, can be strategically placed to monitor traffic flow, vehicle speeds, and occupancy. CCTVs provide visual surveillance of traffic conditions, allowing for real-time monitoring and analysis.

Vehicle-based technology, on the other hand, focuses on gathering data directly from the vehicles themselves. Global Positioning System (GPS) technology is commonly used to track and collect vehicle location information. By utilizing GPS receivers installed in vehicles, precise positioning data can be obtained, enabling the monitoring of travel routes and speeds. Cell-based technologies utilize cellular networks to capture data, such as mobile phone signals and network-based location data. Floating car technologies involve equipping vehicles with dedicated data collection devices to capture information on vehicle movement, speed, and traffic conditions.

These diverse data collection technologies play a crucial role in providing accurate and comprehensive data for ITS applications. By leveraging infrastructure-based and vehicle-based technologies, transportation authorities and researchers can obtain valuable insights into traffic patterns, travel behaviors, and road conditions. This data serves as the foundation for various ITS applications, including traffic management, route optimization, intelligent transportation planning, and real-time traveler information systems.

The continuous evolution and refinement of data collection technologies in ITS contribute to enhancing the overall efficiency, safety, and sustainability of transportation systems. By leveraging these advancements, transportation stakeholders can make informed

decisions and implement effective strategies to alleviate traffic congestion, reduce travel times, improve road safety, and minimize environmental impacts.

Communication technologies:

Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) rely on effective communication technologies to facilitate the exchange of data and information within the transportation ecosystem. There is a wide array of communication technologies available for use in ITS, each with its own characteristics in terms of capacity, cost, and operational strategies.

These communication technologies span a spectrum, ranging from traditional telephone lines to more advanced options such as General Packet Radio Service (GPRS) and various ad hoc wireless communication and wireless broadband technologies. Telephone lines have long been used as a means of communication in transportation systems, providing reliable voice-based communication. However, as technology has progressed, newer and more sophisticated communication methods have emerged.

General Packet Radio Service (GPRS) is a wireless communication technology that enables the transmission of data packets over cellular networks. It offers a higher capacity for data transfer compared to traditional telephone lines, making it suitable for transmitting real-time information in ITS applications. GPRS provides a cost-effective solution for data communication, making it widely adopted in various transportation systems.

In recent years, ad hoc wireless communication and wireless broadband technologies have gained significant popularity in the field of intelligent vehicle communication. Vehicular Ad hoc Networks (VANETs) are a prime example of ad hoc wireless communication, where vehicles form a self-organizing network to exchange information. VANETs utilize vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V) and vehicle-to-infrastructure (V2I) communication to enable the exchange of critical data such as traffic information, road conditions, and safety warnings. This technology plays a crucial role in supporting advanced ITS applications like cooperative collision avoidance and intelligent traffic management.

Wireless broadband technologies, such as 4G and 5G networks, offer high-speed and reliable connectivity for ITS applications. These technologies provide fast and efficient data transfer capabilities, enabling real-time communication between vehicles, infrastructure, and control centers. With their ability to support large-scale data transmission, wireless broadband technologies are instrumental in supporting emerging ITS applications like connected and autonomous vehicles.

By leveraging these diverse communication technologies, ITS systems can facilitate seamless and efficient communication between different components of the transportation ecosystem. The availability of reliable and high-capacity communication channels enables the real-time exchange of critical information, leading to improved traffic management, enhanced safety measures, and more informed decision-making in the field of transportation.

Continued advancements in communication technologies hold the potential to revolutionize the way transportation systems operate, leading to safer, more efficient, and sustainable transportation networks.

Database management:

In the realm of Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS), efficient database management is crucial for handling and organizing the vast amounts of traffic-related information and obtaining a comprehensive overview of the network based on the received data.

Database management plays a pivotal role in ITS by providing a structured framework to store, process, and retrieve information relevant to traffic management and transportation systems. These databases serve as repositories for various types of data, including real-time traffic data, historical traffic patterns, road conditions, incident reports, and other relevant information.

By effectively managing these databases, ITS can leverage the stored data to gain valuable insights and make informed decisions. Traffic-related information, such as vehicle speed, volume, and congestion levels, can be analyzed to identify trends, patterns, and potential bottlenecks in the transportation network. This analysis helps transportation authorities and planners develop strategies for improving traffic flow, optimizing route planning, and enhancing overall network efficiency.

Moreover, database management in ITS enables the integration of disparate data sources. By consolidating information from various sensors, monitoring devices, and communication systems, a holistic view of the transportation network can be established. This integrated database allows for a comprehensive understanding of traffic conditions and facilitates the development of intelligent algorithms and models to support real-time traffic management and predictive analytics.

Furthermore, database management in ITS also supports data sharing and exchange among different stakeholders. Traffic data collected from multiple sources can be processed and shared with relevant entities, including transportation agencies, emergency services, and third-party applications. This data sharing enables collaborative decision-making, fosters coordination among different entities, and promotes the development of innovative applications and services that benefit road users. As the volume and variety of traffic-related data continue to grow, the importance of robust database management becomes increasingly evident. Advances in database technologies, such as cloud-based solutions, distributed databases, and big data analytics, offer opportunities to handle the vast amounts of data generated by ITS systems. These advancements facilitate real-time data processing, improve scalability, and enhance the overall performance of ITS databases.

1.1.1 ITS Applications

The various ITS applications are described as follows:

Traffic Control: It focuses mainly on prioritizing the modes of transport such as buses, cyclist, pedestrians and other emergency vehicles in order to evaluate the performance and study the reasons for traffic emissions and congestion.

Risk management systems: Various technologies are used for this purpose in order to smooth the traffic flow and to provide medical and other related help in such cases.

Vehicle information and navigation systems: In-vehicle information system warns drivers about adverse climate conditions, road surface conditions, traffic jams and hazards including accidents. Navigation systems provide vehicle location information in real time and route guidance for driver to take optimum route.

Driver assistance systems: In order to save the driver from accidents these systems have replaced some human driver decisions with machine decisions which also help to achieve smoother vehicle control.

Air pollution control: Road transport is the major source of air pollution which has caused impact on human health and environment quality. Various models and protocols are used in ITS to control air pollution (6, 7).

1. Methodology

In order to conduct progressive review on ITS, we have searched various digital libraries which include IEEE, ACM, Springer, Science Direct and Google scholar database.

Search Results Filtered vs. Screening Creteria

Fig. 1: Systematic Review used for Intelligent transportation system.

The search was conducted using the term "Intelligent Transport Systems," indicating a focus on the field of intelligent transportation systems. The search results were filtered to include only articles published between 2019 and 2023. This suggests that the aim was to find recent research and developments in the field. Out of the initial search results, 20,860 articles were filtered based on being categorized as research papers. This indicates a preference for scholarly articles and a desire to explore the academic research in intelligent transport systems. From the filtered research papers, 5,517 articles were further screened based on being open access. This suggests that the researcher or reader prioritizes access to freely available content. Among the open access research papers, 1,589 articles were sorted based on their application in engineering fields. This indicates a specific interest in the engineering aspects of intelligent transport systems. A more detailed examination of the articles' relevance was conducted by reading their abstracts. Only 163 articles were deemed relevant based on this evaluation. This suggests a rigorous selection process to narrow down the number of articles for further study. Finalized for Detailed Study: Finally, after the abstract reading and relevance assessment, only 42 articles were selected for detailed study. These articles were considered the most relevant and likely contain information of particular interest for the researcher or reader. The systematic and focused approach in exploring recent scholarly research in the field of intelligent transport

systems, with a specific emphasis on engineering applications. The final selection of 42 articles suggests that the researcher or reader aims to delve deeper into a relatively small number of highly relevant studies.

2. Findings and Discussion

2.1.Sensor Based Technologies

Sensor-based technologies play a crucial role in Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) by collecting and utilizing real-time data to optimize traffic flow, enhance safety, and improve overall transportation efficiency. Several research studies and projects have explored the application of sensor-based technologies in various aspects of ITS.

One study conducted by Shandiz et al. (8) proposed an algorithm for controlling traffic lights based on real-time traffic flow information collected by sensors. The algorithm, which incorporates a Genetic Algorithm (GA), adjusts the timing of green lights to maximize traffic flow and facilitate the smooth movement of vehicles. Through simulation, the study demonstrated that the algorithm effectively utilizes real data to achieve the full capacity of intersections and roads, leading to improved traffic conditions.

Another application of sensor-based technologies in ITS involves monitoring air quality. Air Quality Stations equipped with sensors collect air pollution data, which is then transmitted to a centralized Data Center. Based on this data, the Data Center can request traffic management to implement restrictions, such as reducing the number of vehicles in heavily polluted areas. Additionally, Traffic Monitoring Centers can activate traffic monitoring systems to gather further data on traffic conditions. The Data Center can then request additional buses from public transport management to encourage the use of public transportation as an alternative to private vehicles. Simulation results from this approach showcase the potential for automating air pollution assessment within the ITS framework.

In a project called SMARTY (9), focused on sustainable transport and mobility in smart cities, sensor-based technologies played a vital role in collecting data from social and environmental sensors. The project incorporated a social sensing module, which gathered data from social networks and platforms such as tweets, along with an urban sensing module. These collected data were processed using data mining techniques to extract important information, such as traffic flow and accident data. The utilization of this information allows users to make informed decisions and choose optimal routes based on real-time conditions, ultimately improving their travel experiences. Overall, these examples highlight the diverse applications of sensor-based technologies in ITS. From optimizing traffic light timing to managing air pollution and providing real-time traffic information, sensors play a critical role in collecting and analyzing data to inform decision-making processes within the transportation ecosystem. By harnessing the power of sensor-based technologies, ITS can continue to advance and address various challenges, ultimately leading to more efficient, sustainable, and user-friendly transportation systems.

2.2.System and Platform Based Technologies

System and platform-based technologies are integral components of Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS), offering innovative approaches to analyze data, make informed decisions, and manage transportation systems effectively. Several research studies have explored the application of these technologies in various aspects of ITS. In one study (10), a new framework called Parallel Transportation Management Systems (PTMS) was proposed. PTMS comprises several components that work together to analyze models and make decisions. These

components include the Operator Training System for Transportation (OTST), Dyna CAS (Testing and evaluation component), Agent-based Distributed and Adaptive Platforms for Transportation Systems (ADAPTS), and ITOP (Actual control and management component of traffic equipment and system). The PTMS framework aims to enhance transportation management by providing advanced tools and methodologies for decision-making. Another system, Intelligent Sensor Information System (ISIS), was described in another study (11). ISIS focuses on reducing crime and antisocial behavior in public transport systems through an active Closed-Circuit Television (CCTV) approach. The system utilizes an event composition component to detect and combine small events to deduce events with linguistic meaning. The overall system architecture incorporates on-board event recognition and control room software to generate real-time alerts over a wireless network. By leveraging ISIS, transportation authorities can enhance security measures and mitigate potential risks in public transport environments. Additionally, Alazawi et al. (4) proposed an emergency response system specifically targeting risks in the transportation system. The study integrates technologies such as Vehicular Ad hoc Networks (VANETs), mobile computing, and cloud computing to develop a comprehensive risk management system. The proposed system is evaluated based on its effectiveness in mitigating the impact of risks on the transportation system, and it is compared with traditional risk management systems. By leveraging VANETs and cloud computing, the system offers real-time risk assessment and response capabilities, enabling prompt and effective emergency management.

These examples showcase the utilization of system and platform-based technologies in ITS. From parallel transportation management systems to intelligent sensor information systems and emergency response systems, these technologies provide advanced tools for decision-making, enhance security measures, and improve risk management in transportation systems. By incorporating these innovative approaches, ITS can evolve and optimize its operations, ultimately leading to more efficient, secure, and resilient transportation networks.

2.3. Traffic Management Technologies

Traffic management technologies play a crucial role in Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) by providing efficient solutions for monitoring and controlling traffic conditions. Various research studies have proposed innovative schemes and techniques to enhance traffic management and improve the overall driving experience.

In one study, a scheme was proposed that incorporates a smart city framework to facilitate the sharing of traffic-related information among vehicles and drivers. This framework utilizes Vehicular and Adhoc NETWORK (VANET) technology to establish communication between vehicles and roadside units. The smart city framework includes a warning message module equipped with Intelligent Traffic Lights (ITLs). This module analyzes traffic information, makes decisions regarding route optimization, and informs drivers about the current traffic conditions. By leveraging this scheme, drivers can make informed decisions and choose appropriate routes, leading to improved traffic flow and reduced congestion.

Another study (12) focused on providing accurate GPS information for land vehicle monitoring systems. The proposed technique incorporates GPS integrity checks at different levels to ensure the quality of the GPS positioning output. GPS Doppler information is utilized to verify the integrity of a vehicle's velocity, which in turn improves the results of the map matching process. The final step involves confirming the accuracy of the algorithm used for map matching. By implementing this scheme, the reliability and accuracy of GPS-based land

vehicle monitoring systems can be significantly enhanced, enabling more precise tracking and monitoring of vehicles. These examples illustrate the advancements in traffic management technologies within the realm of ITS. By incorporating smart city frameworks, VANET communication, and GPS integrity checks, transportation authorities and researchers are striving to create more efficient and reliable traffic management systems. These technologies not only improve traffic flow and reduce congestion but also enhance the accuracy of vehicle monitoring and navigation, ultimately leading to safer and more streamlined transportation networks. Continued research and development in traffic management technologies hold the potential to revolutionize the way we navigate and manage traffic in the future.

2.4. Traffic Risk Reduction Technologies

In a study (13), the focus was on improving decision-making tools for natural risks. The researchers described the development and implementation of an Intelligent Risk Decision Support System (IDDSS), specifically highlighting its capabilities in responding to and planning for floods. By utilizing IDDSS, the concept of risk, susceptibility, and resilience in risk management can be enhanced, leading to more effective and informed decision-making processes in the face of natural disasters.

Another proposal (14) introduced an intelligent traffic control system that aims to optimize traffic flow and improve overall road management. Each vehicle in the system is equipped with a Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) tag that cannot be removed, and these tags can only be read by RFID readers. The RFID readers also count the number of vehicles during specific durations to determine network congestion. Based on this information, the duration of green lights for particular paths can be adjusted accordingly. The system also utilizes a Zigbee module (CC2500) to enable wireless communication between emergency vehicles, such as ambulances, and the traffic controller. Experimental results from a prototype of the system demonstrated its effectiveness in various input scenarios, showcasing its potential in improving traffic management and assisting in the detection of stolen vehicles. The role of telematics in the transport system was discussed in another study (15). Telematics has the capability to strengthen the positive aspects of transportation while mitigating its negative impacts. It aids in reducing various transport-related issues, including air pollution, energy consumption, and congestion, without requiring additional contributions. By integrating telematics into the transport system, improvements can be made in terms of efficiency, sustainability, and overall environmental impact.

The evolution of vehicles from simple sensors to a network of autonomous vehicles was explored in (16). Similar to the concept of the Internet of Things (IoT), these autonomous vehicles possess intelligence, storage capabilities, and learning tendencies to interact with users. Equipped with sensors that receive external information, these vehicles assist drivers and employ software for navigation, pollution control, and traffic management. The underlying concept behind this transition is the vehicular cloud. Simulation results demonstrated that this scheme outperformed existing approaches, as it does not disrupt existing Intelligent Transport System (ITS) applications unless VANET congestion is detected.

In an effort to alleviate the effects of congestion caused by traffic jams and provide guidance to road users, a new strategy called Weighted Congestion Coefficient Feedback Strategy (WCCFS) was introduced in (18). This technique generates dynamic information that can be displayed to guide users on the road. Simulation results were compared with three existing technologies, and the findings showed that WCCFS outperformed the others in terms of improving road conditions and alleviating congestion effects. To aid government agencies in emergency planning, a plan was proposed in (19) to develop an Artificial Emergency

Planning System (AELPS). AELPS utilizes artificial society theory based on agent-based modeling to describe the characteristics of various elements within the emergency system. It integrates multiple subsystems, including pollution, medical and rescue, geology, weather, epidemiology, and transportation, to provide comprehensive risk relief and aid in emergency planning. In an effort to minimize fuel consumption and emissions, Alsabaan et al. (7) focused on creating an Economical and Environment Friendly Geo cast (EEFG) protocol. This protocol integrates vehicular networks with fuel models such as the Comprehensive Modal Emissions Model (CMEM) and Virginia Tech Microscopic model (VT-Micro), along with Geo cast protocols. The idea behind this approach is to transmit Traffic Light Signal (TLS) related information to vehicles in order to reduce emissions and fuel consumption. The combination of Geo cast protocols with TLS plays a crucial role in this model. The VT-Microscopic model is utilized to measure fuel consumption and CO₂ emissions, enabling vehicles to calculate environmentally friendly

2.5. Modelling and Simulation Based Technologies

Modelling and simulation-based technologies have been explored in various studies to enhance intelligent transportation systems. One approach (20) aims to combine agent-based traffic management with cloud computing. By utilizing the adaptability and mobility of mobile agents, traffic issues can be effectively addressed. The concept of an intelligent transportation cloud is introduced, which provides ample storage, computing resources, decision support, and an environment for traffic management strategies. The integration of mobile agents also requires computing and power resources, which can be fulfilled through cloud computing. However, the adoption of vehicular clouds (VCs) presents privacy and security challenges that need to be addressed. These challenges include vehicle authentication, tangled locations and identities, and establishing trust relationships. To tackle these issues, a directional security scheme is proposed to ensure the secure functioning of VCs. In another study (21), a rule-based iterative Artificial Transportation System (ATS) design process is presented. The ATS employs synthetic traffic simulations to address traffic issues from a complex system perspective. The simulations are conducted using a prototype that consists of a multi-agent platform. This prototype can generate various traffic behaviors, such as congestion, and aids in evaluating traffic rules and regulations.

A universal framework based on evaluated hybrid Assisted GPS (A-GPS) and Uplink Time Difference Of Arrival (U-TDOA) is proposed in (22) for real-time road transport data collection systems. This framework, which incorporates artificial neural networks (ANN), integrates multiple technologies for traffic data collection, state analysis, processing analysis, presentation of traffic flow information, and optimization. The data analysis component introduces a new approach called "Pinpoint-Temporal" sampling frequency method, enhancing the accuracy of data analysis. To improve accident management, a service-based Intelligent Transportation System Framework (s-ITSF) is proposed in (23). The s-ITSF utilizes Vehicular Cloud Computing (VCC) to provide efficient accident management services, including before/after accident management and traffic information dissemination. The framework includes an Accident Management Center (AMC) to assess the level of damage, an Accident Management Organization (AMO) to provide facilities in accident areas, and a Transportation and Accident Database Center (TADC) to collect and manage traffic information for accident prevention.

Lastly, in (24), a prototype is proposed to address the challenges of traffic management. Unfortunately, the provided information ends abruptly, and further details about the prototype are not available. The simulation model comprises several sub-models, which simulate the number of vehicles arriving and leaving roads based on inter-arrival and inter-departure times.

Each sub-model represents a road with three intersections. The simulation results indicate that the waiting time for cars at different intersections decreases when the durations of red and green lights are kept constant. The simulation model performs optimally when the inter-departure time at the three intersections is set to 0.6 seconds. In another study (25), a proposed model aims to integrate cloud computing and vehicular networks for the purpose of sharing computational resources. The architecture includes a central cloud, vehicular cloud, and roadside cloud. Resource allocation in the cloud is achieved using a game theoretical approach, while virtual machine migration is facilitated through a resource reservation method. Experimental results demonstrate a significant reduction in service dropping rate.

In a separate work (26), within the CAPLOC project (2010-2013), a method is proposed to combine signal propagation and image processing techniques. Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) in conjunction with GPS offer cost-effective global positioning solutions. However, these systems can sometimes produce incorrect results due to signal processing conditions. To address this, a laboratory vehicle equipped with two GNSS receivers and a fisheye camera is used. Images of the sky are captured using the camera mounted on the vehicle's roof. The positions of the vehicle and a reference trajectory are obtained using the GNSS receivers. By utilizing information from the captured images, obstacles and non-line-of-sight (NLOS) signals can be effectively evaluated to mitigate various errors. Furthermore, in another proposal (27), a Vehicular SMS System (VSS) is introduced to address issues such as traffic congestion and road accidents. The VSS employs the cellular network concept by utilizing SMS systems to provide services in Vehicular Ad-Hoc Networks (VANETs). Compared to VANETs, VSS offers a more cost-effective solution. However, further research is required to address privacy and trust concerns.

Table 1. Summary of various transport issues covered in literature survey

R f. No.	Transport Related Issues identified in the literature study							traffic crash
	Traffic Control	Air Pollution	Crime control	Efficient navigation	Congestion control	Resource management	Risk Management	
1	Y		Y	Y	Y			
2	Y			Y	Y			
3								Y
4								Y
5				Y				
6							Y	
7	Y	Y			Y			
8	Y					Y		
9	Y			Y	Y			Y
10	Y			Y	Y	Y		
11	Y			Y	Y			
12						Y		
13						Y		Y
14				Y		Y		
15				Y	Y			
16		Y				Y		
17	Y			Y	Y			
18	Y							Y

19						Y		
20	Y							Y
21	Y							Y
22						Y		
23	Y							Y
24	Y							Y
25	Y							

Traffic Control: Traffic control is a critical issue in transportation systems, especially in urban areas with high vehicle volumes. Effective traffic control measures aim to regulate the flow of vehicles, minimize congestion, and ensure the safety and efficiency of road networks. Techniques such as traffic signals, roundabouts, lane markings, and intelligent transportation systems (ITS) are utilized to manage traffic flow and optimize intersections.

Air Pollution: Transportation is a significant contributor to air pollution, emitting pollutants such as particulate matter, nitrogen oxides, and carbon monoxide. The high concentration of vehicles on roads leads to increased emissions and environmental degradation. Strategies to address air pollution from transportation include promoting electric and hybrid vehicles, implementing emission standards, improving public transportation systems, and encouraging alternative modes of transportation like cycling and walking.

Crime Control: Crime control in transportation systems involves addressing issues such as theft, vandalism, and safety concerns for passengers and drivers. Security measures like surveillance cameras, well-lit stations and parking areas, and increased police presence can help deter criminal activities. Additionally, integrating smart technologies and real-time monitoring systems can enhance security and ensure passenger safety in public transport networks.

Efficient Navigation: Efficient navigation systems are essential for providing accurate and timely route guidance to drivers, reducing travel time, and minimizing congestion. Advanced navigation technologies, such as GPS (Global Positioning System) and real-time traffic information, assist drivers in selecting optimal routes, avoiding traffic bottlenecks, and improving overall travel efficiency. These systems can also incorporate alternative transportation modes and promote multimodal integration.

Congestion Control: Congestion occurs when the demand for transportation exceeds the capacity of the road network, resulting in reduced speeds, increased travel times, and decreased efficiency. Congestion control strategies involve traffic management techniques like intelligent traffic signal systems, dynamic lane assignment, congestion pricing, and promoting public transportation and carpooling. Advanced technologies, including traffic flow modeling and real-time data analysis, can enable proactive congestion management.

Resource Management: Resource management in transportation focuses on optimizing the allocation and utilization of various resources, including fuel, infrastructure, vehicles, and personnel. Effective resource management strategies aim to minimize waste, improve operational efficiency, and reduce costs. This involves techniques like route optimization, fleet management systems, maintenance scheduling, and intelligent logistics planning to ensure optimal resource utilization.

Risk Management: Risk management in transportation involves identifying, assessing, and mitigating risks associated with accidents, natural disasters, and other unforeseen events. This includes measures such as improving road safety infrastructure, implementing driver education and training programs, enforcing traffic regulations, and developing emergency response plans. Advanced technologies like vehicle-to-vehicle communication and collision avoidance systems contribute to enhanced risk management in transportation systems.

Addressing these traffic and transportation issues requires a multidimensional approach that combines technological advancements, policy interventions, and behavioral changes. Integrated solutions involving data-driven approaches, smart technologies, and efficient transportation planning are crucial for creating sustainable and safe transportation systems.

Table 2. Summary of techniques and technologies used to solve transport related issues

R f. Techniques and Technologies								
No.	Sensors	Agent based computing	Vehicular cloud computing	VANET/ VSS	RFID readers	Advance GPS	Smart traffic lights	IRIS
1	Y						Y	
2							Y	
3								Y
4			Y					
5					Y	Y		
6				Y				
7		Y					Y	
8		Y	Y					
9	Y	Y					Y	
10					Y	Y	Y	
11			Y		Y			
12				Y				
13	Y					Y		
14			Y					
15	Y		Y					
16		Y	Y					
17	Y				Y			
18	Y							
19			Y					
20						Y		
21			Y					
22			Y		Y			
23	Y							
24	Y		Y					
25					Y			

Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) are advanced technological solutions that aim to improve transportation efficiency, safety, and sustainability. Several key components and technologies contribute to the effectiveness of ITS, including sensors, agent-based computing,

vehicular cloud computing, VANET/VSS, RFID, advanced GPS, and smart traffic lights. Let's discuss each of these components:

Sensors: Sensors play a crucial role in ITS by collecting real-time data from various sources such as vehicles, infrastructure, and the environment. They can monitor traffic flow, detect incidents, measure air quality, and provide valuable information for decision-making and optimization of transportation systems.

Agent-based computing: Agent-based computing involves the use of intelligent software agents that can interact with each other and the environment to accomplish specific tasks. In the context of ITS, these agents can collect and process data, make intelligent decisions, and communicate with other agents or systems to optimize traffic management, route planning, and resource allocation.

Vehicular cloud computing: Vehicular cloud computing leverages the power of cloud computing in the context of vehicles and transportation systems. It allows vehicles to offload computationally intensive tasks to the cloud, enabling advanced analytics, data processing, and decision-making. Vehicular cloud computing can facilitate efficient traffic management, real-time navigation, and personalized services for drivers and passengers.

VANET/VSS: VANET (Vehicular Ad-Hoc Network) and VSS (Vehicular SMS System) are communication systems designed specifically for vehicles. VANET enables vehicles to communicate with each other and with infrastructure, facilitating the exchange of information about traffic conditions, hazards, and other relevant data. VSS utilizes cellular network concepts and SMS systems to provide services within VANETs, offering a cost-effective alternative for communication.

RFID (Radio Frequency Identification): RFID technology uses electromagnetic fields to automatically identify and track objects. In transportation systems, RFID tags can be attached to vehicles, containers, or infrastructure elements to enable automatic identification and tracking. This technology finds applications in toll collection, vehicle tracking, and supply chain management.

Advanced GPS: Advanced GPS (Global Positioning System) technologies enhance traditional GPS capabilities by providing more accurate and reliable positioning information. These systems employ additional sensors, such as multiple GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) receivers, to improve positioning accuracy, especially in challenging environments where signal conditions may be degraded.

Smart traffic lights: Smart traffic lights are equipped with sensors and advanced control algorithms to optimize traffic flow and reduce congestion. These lights can dynamically adjust their signal timings based on real-time traffic conditions, reducing waiting times, improving traffic efficiency, and enhancing overall transportation system performance.

The intelligent transportation systems incorporate various technologies such as sensors, agent-based computing, vehicular cloud computing, VANET/VSS, RFID, advanced GPS, and smart traffic lights. These components work together to enable data collection, efficient communication, advanced analytics, and optimized decision-making in transportation systems, leading to improved safety, reduced congestion, and enhanced user experience.

3. Conclusion

Due to population growth, traffic has increased, resulting in a range of challenges including traffic control, air pollution, crime control, risk management, congestion control, and navigation system efficiency. Table 1 provides an overview of these issues as highlighted in the literature review. The analysis of Table 1 reveals that the primary challenges in most studies related to Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) are traffic control, congestion control, and traffic management. Conversely, researchers have placed less emphasis on air pollution, crime control, efficient navigation, and resource management.

To address these transport issues, researchers have proposed various technologies and techniques that rely on real-time information. This includes the utilization of active CCTV cameras and sensors to provide real-time data. Moreover, GPS technology has been integrated with image processing techniques to develop advanced navigation systems. Additionally, advanced technologies like VANETs, cloud computing, and agent-based computing have been introduced to enhance the efficiency and intelligence of transport systems. Table 2 summarizes the techniques employed by researchers to tackle transport issues. Although researchers are exploring several approaches, sensors, VANETs, vehicular cloud computing, and agent-based techniques have proven to be the most effective solutions in the current scenario. As technology advances, other techniques such as advanced GPS, smart traffic lights, and RFID readers may prove beneficial for further improvements.

To address challenges like air pollution, congestion, and accidents, there is a need for an improved and intelligent transport system known as Intelligent Transport System (ITS). ITS incorporates various technologies such as data collection, communication, machine learning, and data mining to provide transport-related services, including traffic control, navigation systems, driver assistance, and fault detection. Furthermore, ITS addresses issues like risk management, congestion control, and air pollution. The advancement of ITS involves the integration of new techniques like the Internet of Vehicles, vehicular cloud computing, and agent-based computing, which includes the implementation of Artificial Transport Systems. By combining these techniques, ITS can become more efficient in resolving transport-related problems.

4. Conflict of Interest

Authors have no conflict of interest.

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